

ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS ALLIANCE

2024 ANNUAL REPORT

Group Photo from the 7th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium - Photo credit Kyle Klein

Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance

2024 ANNUAL REPORT

GRATITUDE

A message from the co-chairs of the AVE executive committee

Dear Colleagues,

We are thrilled to share the progress and achievements of the Alliance in 2024. Our journey towards mapping variant effects and creating a comprehensive Atlas of Variant Effects has been nothing short of remarkable.

This year, we:

1. Expanded our geographic reach to include members from 50 countries.
2. Enhanced the MaveDB platform with new visualizations, streamlined workflows, and downstream data integrations.
3. Launched the Alliance-sponsored "Variants and Us" podcast with colleagues at the University of Toronto.
4. Provided valuable educational materials and resources, including guidelines for variant effect predictor use and interpretation, as well as guidelines for using functional evidence in clinical practice.

These advancements, along with a remarkable 40% increase in MAVE data deposition from the previous year, showcase our collective dedication to improve disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment through genomic insights.

We extend our deepest gratitude to all members, collaborators, and supporters for their unwavering commitment and contributions. Together, we are building a future where we can profoundly impact human health.

With warm regards,

Matt Hurles and Doug Fowler

Handwritten signatures of Matt Hurles and Doug Fowler in black ink.

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THE ALLIANCE

The Atlas of Variant Effects (AVE) Alliance, founded in 2020, is an international collaboration dedicated to developing, disseminating, and democratizing technologies for mapping variant effects. Our vision is to create a comprehensive atlas of variant effect maps for key regions of human and pathogen genomes to aid in the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of diseases.

We unite genomics researchers, curators, health practitioners and funders from around the world to set standards, share tools, and strategize. Our goal is to facilitate the creation of comprehensive variant effect maps and establish community-driven resources for sharing and analyzing large-scale variant effect data.

OUR VALUES AND PRINCIPLES

- Inclusivity
- Open Access Science
- Research Excellence and Integrity
- Respect, Relevance, Reciprocity, Responsibility, Relationships

LEADERSHIP AND STAFF

Executive Committee: David Adams, Benedetta Bolognesi, Anna Gloyn, Irene Gallego Romero, Matthew Hurles (co-chair), Doug Fowler (co-chair), Deborah Marks, J.T. Neal, Frederick 'Fritz' Roth, Alan Rubin, Lea Starita

Executive Office Staff:

Lara Muffley and Alex Hopkins

Communications Working Group:

Lara Muffley, Dean Owen, Rachael Smith, Alexandra Canet

Variant Effect Seminar Series Organizing Committee:

Priyanka Bajaj, Ohanna Bezerra, Matteo Cagiada, Ziyi Dai, Mariano Martín, Jingyou Rao, Adelaide Tovar

Workstream co-chairs:

- Lea Starita and Clare Turnbull - Clinical Variant Interpretation (CVI)
- Alan Rubin and Julia Foreman - Data Coordination and Dissemination (DCD)
- Andrew Glazer and Alex Nguyen Ba - Experimental Technology and Standards (ETS)
- Joseph Marsh - Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP)

AT A GLANCE

Established

700+
members

50
countries

3
committees

4
work-streams

>10
Online
resources
and toolkits

65 Variant
Effects Seminar
Series speakers

7
Mutational
Scanning
Symposiums

167
educational
videos

968
youtube
subscribers

4
podcast
episodes

300+
MAVE
Registry
Projects

>1K
score sets
deposited
in MAVEDB

41K
unique
visitors

HIGHLIGHTS FROM 2024

New Resources

- [Clinical Application of MAVEs](#)
- [AVE Zenodo Community space](#)

Collaborative Publications

- [Using multiplexed functional data to reduce variant classification inequities in underrepresented populations](#)
- [Guidelines for releasing a variant effect predictor](#)
- [Minimum information and guidelines for reporting a multiplexed assay of variant effect](#)

Leadership changes

- [Julia Foreman](#) joined [Alan Rubin](#) as co-chair of the DCD workstream (Aug 2024)
- [Benedetta Bolognesi](#), previous co-chair for ETS workstream, handed over the baton to [Alex Nguyen Ba](#) (Nov 2024)
- [Debbie Marks](#) stepped down from the AVE Executive Committee (Dec 2024)

Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop

- [7th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) (May 22-24th, 2024) Broad Institute, Cambridge, USA with 240 attendees from 14 countries

Variant Effects Seminar Series (VESS)

- [65 speakers](#) from 2020-2024
- [Organizing committee](#)
 - Newest: Priyanka Bajaj, Matteo Cagiada, Ziyi Dai, Jingyou Rao, Adelaide Tovar
 - Departures: Diego Calderon, Yann Ilboudo, Adrine de Souza

Variants and Us Podcast (new!)

- [4 episodes](#) (Transcripts and show notes available on [Zenodo](#))
- [VUS Pod Instagram](#)

Educational videos and featured talks

- [Youtube channel](#) Over 160 videos, 968 subscribers and over 60K views, includes talks from previous Symposiums, Seminar Series and more!
- [MAVE Education Project](#) (Functional evidence use in clinical practice)

Social Media presence

- [LinkedIn](#) and [BlueSky](#)

MEMBERSHIP GROWTH

The Alliance exceeded 700 members from 50 nations in 2024. These individuals include early and mid-career scientists, along with senior-level individuals in industry, government, and academia, as well as patient advocacy groups and foundations - a total of more than 375 institutions. The majority (80 percent) serve in the academic sector.

WORKSTREAM PROGRESS

All workstreams and committees have been making strides in setting standards, providing tools, and disseminating information to advance the field of variant effect mapping.

4 interconnected workstreams

Guide
Experimental
Technologies
and Standards
(ETS)

Led by Andrew Glazer
& Alex Nguyen Ba

Analyze-Predict
Analysis,
Modeling and
Prediction
(AMP)

Led by
Joseph Marsh

Translate
Clinical
Variant
Interpretation
(CVI)

Led by Lea Starita
& Clare Turnbull

Share
Data
Coordination &
Dissemination
(DCD)

Led by Alan Rubin
& Julia Foreman

The **Experimental Technology and Standards (ETS) workstream** led by Alex Ngyuen Ba (University of Toronto) and Andrew Glazer (Vanderbilt University) facilitates the development, scaling, evaluation, comparison and dissemination of new MAVE methods.

This year, the group:

- Developed minimum information standards for MAVEs and a controlled vocabulary in conjunction with the DCD workstream ([Minimum information and guidelines for reporting a multiplexed assay of variant effect](#)).
- Established an [AVE protocols.io workspace](#) for MAVE protocols collection (including a companion [guide](#) and how to [video](#)).
- Added new members: Kenneth Matreyek (Case Western), Sven Diederichs (DKFZ | University Hospital Freiburg), Guillaume Diss (Friedrich Miescher Institute), Andrea Martella (AstraZeneca) and Daniel O’Neill (AstraZeneca), Aleksandr Zakirov (EMBL-EBI).

But why?

PUBLICIZE YOUR SCIENCE

HELP OTHERS DO MAVE EXPERIMENTS

Atlas of Variant Effects MAVE Protocols Collection Tutorial

The **Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP) workstream** led by Joseph Marsh (The University of Edinburgh) promotes the development of computational tools and standards.

In 2024, this workstream, in close collaboration with other members of the AVE Alliance, produced a manuscript called "[Guidelines for releasing a variant effect predictor](#)", which offers compressive recommendations for developing and disseminating computational variant effect predictors (VEPs). The guidelines emphasize the importance of open-source availability, transparent methodologies, clear interpretation of variant effect scores, standardized scales, accessible predictions and thorough disclosure of training to data. By promoting adherence to these principles, we hope to enhance the usability and interpretability of VEPs, facilitate their integration into various analysis pipelines, and encourage their adoption within the scientific community.

Plans for 2025 include further work on computational tools for the analysis of MAVE data as well as the release of a target priority list. This list will identify proteins where performing a MAVE is likely to yield the the greatest benefit, in part based on poor agreement across computational approaches.

The **Clinical Variant Interpretation (CVI) workstream** led by Clare Turnbull (ICR) and Lea Starita (Brotman Baty Institute / University of Washington) helps to resolve issues relating to the use of MAVE data to interpret human genetic variants.

Evaluating MAVE Functional Assays
Guidance on how to use Functional Evidence in your Clinical Practice

Functional Evidence (and how to use it)

Interested in how to use Functional Evidence?

Workshop(s) covering central recommendations and guidelines on functional evidence use (Richards et al, 2015 and Brnich et al, 2019) along with recommendations on evaluating MAVE functional assays.

- **Workshop Nov 2023: Functional evidence and how to use it** (Villani & Spurdle)
<https://zenodo.org/records/13129941> (slides)
[Functional evidence and how to use it](#) (<<Video tutorial)
- **Workshop June 2024: Functional evidence evaluation** (Villani & Spurdle)
<https://zenodo.org/records/13131424> (slides)
[Functional evidence evaluation](#) (<<Video tutorial)

The workshop activities mentioned above are part of the MAVE Education Project. The MAVE Education Project aims to support increased use of functional data/evidence, especially with the increasing body of high throughput functional data. It is an Australian research project funded by the Medical Research Future Fund, APP2015946. The workshop was co-designed, informed by representatives of identified stakeholders in the MAVE Education Project and represents part of a developing project supporting functional evidence use.

Functional evidence

FUNCTIONAL EVIDENCE EVALUATION WORKSHOP

This year, the group [organized resources](#) and held workshops in Australia and Italy on how to use functional evidence in clinical practice. Additional workshops are scheduled at the Curating the Clinical Genome meeting in Hinxton, UK, June 2025. A workshop that focuses on publishing MAVE datasets for clinical use will be held at the 2025 Mutational Scanning Symposium.

CVI is also actively developing recommendations and outlining use cases for combining multiple MAVE datasets in order to improve pathogenicity classification.

Starting in early 2025, CVI members will nucleate [ClinGen's](#) new Functional Working Group that will focus on:

- Approaches for calibration of functional assays for use in variant classification
- Guiding Variant Curation Expert Panel (VCEP) use of multiplexed assays of variant effects (MAVE) data
- Facilitating the development and testing of VCEP curated variants in MAVE and other functional assays
- Informing priorities of large-scale efforts to generate functional data as well as functional data model development
- Providing input on how to effectively integrate functional data into ClinGen tools

The **Data Coordination and Dissemination (DCD)** workstream led by Alan Rubin (WEHI, University of Melbourne) and Julia Foreman (DECIPHER, EMBL-EBI) promotes the growth of the MAVE field by enabling sharing and management of MAVE data. In 2024, this workstream:

- Published [Minimum information and guidelines for reporting a Multiplexed Assay of Variant Effect](#) Claussnitzer et al, Genome Biology, April 2024 (Collaboration with ETS workstream members).

- Helped to enable broad collaboration and data exchange among MaveDB, ClinGen Linked Data Hub, Ensembl, Shariant, DECIPHER, the Broad Institute Genomics 2 Proteins portal, and the UCSC Genome Browser.
- Put additional efforts into education and outreach efforts. Examples include:
 - [MaveDB: discovery and interpretation of high-throughput functional assay data](#) - Australia BioCommons Webinar (Alan Rubin)
 - [Interpreting Genomic Variation: Overcoming Challenges in Diverse Populations](#) - Wellcome Connecting Science (Julia Foreman is one of the course instructors)

CROSS CONSORTIA COLLABORATIONS

The National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI) led **Trans-variant Working Group** was established in 2023 in order to improve communication and achieve synergies in the gathering, analysis and clinical use of variant functional data. This group includes representatives from various initiatives such as [ClinGen](#), [GREGoR](#), [HPRC](#), [IGVF](#) and the AVE Alliance. This group meets on a regular basis by zoom.

A 2024 work product "[Using multiplexed functional data to reduce variant classification inequities in underrepresented populations](#)" which originated within the Atlas of Variant Effects (AVE) is now published in Genome Medicine.

PUBLICATIONS

Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance was cited or mentioned in the following Scientific Publications in 2024.

- [Executive summary from the Clinical Atlas of Variant Effects meeting](#)
- [Variation to biology: optimizing functional analysis of cancer risk variants](#)
- [High-throughput assays to assess variant effects on disease](#)
- [Analyzing the functional effects of DNA variants with gene editing](#)
- [Variant effect predictor correlation with functional assays is reflective of clinical classification performance](#)
- [Guidelines for Releasing a Variant Effect Predictor](#)
- [Minimum information and guidelines for reporting a Multiplexed Assay of Variant Effect](#)
- [Using multiplexed functional data to reduce variant classification inequities in underrepresented populations](#)
- [Workshop report: the clinical application of data from multiplex assays of variant effect](#)
- [Ensembl 2024](#)

MUTATIONAL SCANNING SYMPOSIUM

Each year, the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance hosts the Mutational Scanning Symposium. The [7th annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) was held in May at the Broad Institute in Boston, USA. This year, the three-day program included keynote talks by Heidi Rehm and Vijay G. Sankaran. There were a total of 240 attendees from 14 countries. Sponsors for the event were the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, Illumina, AstraZeneca, CIFAR, ManifoldBio, Octant, protocols.io, SEISMIC, and the Brotman Baty Institute for Precision Medicine.

You can read more details about the symposium in the articles linked below:

[MSS 2024: Recap and Observations from Sumaiya Iqbal and Doug Fowler](#)

[Q&A with Drs. Heidi Rehm and Vijay Sankaran, Keynote Speakers at the 2024 Mutational Scanning Symposium](#)

[Q&A with JT Neal on Planning for the 2024 Mutational Scanning Symposium](#)

Save the dates!

8th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium

May 21-23rd, 2025

Institute for Bioengineering of Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

9th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium

March 2025

SVI, Melbourne, Australia

CLINICAL ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS WORKSHOP

On July 23rd, 2024, researchers, clinicians, and funders convened to outline a vision for a draft atlas of variant effects by 2030, focusing on resolving Variants of Uncertain Significance (VUS). The interactive workshop [held at the University of Pittsburgh](#), delved into measurement and prediction strategies, integrating data from various assays across labs, and the pivotal role of AI in guiding experiments and predicting outcomes. Discussions also covered resource allocation and formulated recommended actions for the community. The [meeting summary can be found here](#).

VARIANT EFFECTS SEMINAR SERIES

This seminar series is a platform for early career scientists to share their research related to interpreting human genetic variation. In September of 2024, VESS celebrated its three-year anniversary!

Seminars are open to the public and recordings are posted to our YouTube channel.

The top five most viewed videos in 2024 were:

- ▶ ["Bridge RNAs direct programmable recombination of target and donor DNA"](#)
Matthew Durrant & Nicholas Perry (2.4K views)
- ▶ ["Leveraging single-cell transcriptomics to study complex diseases"](#)
Annique Claringbould (1.6K views)
- ▶ ["Understanding complex genotype-phenotype maps"](#)
Carlos Marti Gomez (1.5K views)
- ▶ ["Disease variant prediction with deep generative models of evolutionary data"](#)
Jonathan Frazer and Mafalda Dias (over 1.4K views)
- ▶ ["Modeling higher-order genetic interactions in sequence-function relationships"](#)
Juannan Zhou (1.1K views)

Current members of the [VESS Organizing Committee](#) are: Priyanka Bajaj, Ohanna Bezerra, Matteo Cagiada, Ziyi Dai, Mariano Martín, Jingyou Rao, and Adelaide Tovar.

The Alliance also sends thanks to all previous VESS organizing committee members (Diego Calderon, Adrine de Souza, Steven Erwood, Yann Ilboudo and Mireia Seuma) who have helped make our series so successful.

PODCAST

In May we announced a new AVE Alliance sponsored podcast led by Alex Nguyen Ba and team at the University of Toronto. This audio program helps to increase awareness of the basic and translational science necessary to map the effect of variants in disease and rare disease.

- Episode 1 “Variant Effect What?”
Stan Fields, Doug Fowler and Greg Costain
- Episode 2 “Melanoma and Variant Effects: Beyond Sunscreen”
Dave Adams and Jiyeon Choi
- Episode 3 “Your genes on drugs: context matter”
Frederick ‘Fritz’ Roth, Iris Cohn & Michelle Axford

A bonus episode “Live from the Mutational Scanning Symposium” includes interviews with in person attendees: William Buchser, Matteo Cagiada, Matthew Deyell, Justin Kinney, and Nahum Smith

VUSpod stats

7 interviews
3 episodes

Spotify

200+ listens
70+ followers

Listeners: 40% from the US,
25% from Canada, 13% from
the UK, 5% from Spain

 [U of T Scientists Launch New Podcast on Genetic Variants and Rare Diseases](#)

 [New Science Podcast Focuses on Genetic Variants and Rare Diseases](#)

Listen on our website <https://www.varianteffect.org/podcast>

Listen on Spotify! <https://tinyurl.com/VUSPod>

Follow [VUS Pod on Instagram](#)

MAVE RESOURCES AND TOOLS

Multiplexed assays of variant effects (MAVEs) allow the assessment (in a single experiment) of thousands of variants simultaneously. This technique, which harnesses the power of next-gen sequencing, yields large-scale data sets that can shed light on the functional consequences of protein variants and ultimately on the landscape of human genetic variation. The Alliance shares and continually updates a suite of resources and tools for variant effect mapping.

MAVEDB

MaveDB is the open source database for sharing MAVE data. Over the past year, data submissions have increased by 40%. Currently there are nearly 2,000 public datasets containing over 7 Million variants, with roughly half targeting human sequences. Updates to the platform in 2024 included new automatically-generated visualizations and an improved workflow for user data submissions.

This year, **downstream integrations of MaveDB data** included:

- UCSC Genome Browser Track (MAVE data added as a track hub)
- Genomics 2 Protein Portal (scores visible as heatmaps for available genes)
- [Ensembl](#) Variant Effect Predictor (MaveDB integration) ([MaveDB plugin](#))

The complete set of MAVE data (now licensed under Creative Commons Zero) can be downloaded from [Zenodo](#).

MaveDB

The database for sharing MAVE data

- Over 7 Million Variants
- Auto-generated visualizations
- Variant classification pages
- Represented in UCSC genome browser

MAVE REGISTRY

[MaveRegistry](#) is our collaborative resource for sharing progress on Variant Effect Mapping. Over 300 MAVE projects from approximately 60 groups around the world have been publicly registered to date.

EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

With the goal of making MAVEs more accessible, the ETS workstream has established an [AVE protocols.io workspace](#) which currently includes the following protocols:

- Saturation Genome Editing
- Multiplexed Surface Tethering of Extracellular Proteins (MultiSTEP)
- High Efficiency Yeast Library Transformation
- DIMPLE library generation and assembly protocol
- Converting ssDNA oligos to dsDNA with T4 DNA polymerase
- sgRNA library re-amplification in liquid culture
- Rapid and robust cloning of sgRNA expression plasmids

And more!

We encourage all AVE members to share their SOPs. If you would like to contribute a protocol to this collection please see [this guide](#) , [this video](#), or contact Alex Nguyen Ba or Andrew Glazer on the AVE slack channel to learn more.

The Alliance also provides **educational videos** which are free to view on our [youtube channel](#). Popular videos include an [Animated Introduction to Deep Mutational Scanning](#) (over 1.5K views) and [Deep Mutational Scanning workshop](#) (2.8K views)

- [Variant Effects Seminar Series Playlist](#)
- [Mutational Scanning Symposium Playlists](#)
- [MAVE Educational Project Playlist](#)

MAKING MAPS

Our global community has been busy making Variant Effect Maps!

Top Panel: Nahum Smith (Starita Lab BBI University of Washington, USA), Adrine de Souza (Roth Lab, University of Toronto, Canada).
Bottom Panel: Mireia Seuma with Trinidad Sanmartín (Bolognesi Lab, IBEC, Spain) and Hasan Çubuk with Marcin Plech (Marsh Lab, University of Edinburgh, Scotland).

KUDOS AND SHOUTOUTS

“What stands out to me most is how welcoming the AVE community has been. As someone who sort of stumbled into MAVEs from a background in low-throughput functional characterization of rare epilepsy variants, I was worried that I might find the AVE community to be unwelcoming to newcomers, but nothing could be further from the truth. I attended my first in person Mutational Scanning Symposium in Cambridge in 2023. Since then, I've met many amazing AVE community members who inspire me and all of them have been encouraging. I have found that the community is approachable and happy to share advice and hard-earned wisdom. I have the deepest level of respect for the AVE community and hope I can continue to be a contributing member throughout my career.”
Jeff Calhoun - Research Assistant Professor | Northwestern University

“The Atlas of Variant Effect Alliance has served as a platform for me to access and learn how to use MAVE-specific resources, databases and data analysis pipelines. This includes tools like the MAVE registry and pacybara (PacBio barcode clustering pipelines). These have been invaluable to me in generating our genetic variant libraries for my MAVE thesis project.” Emma Scritchfield - PhD student | Schaffer lab Case Western University

“The VESS presentations and recordings have been a staple of my own introduction to the Deep Mutational Scanning field over the past few years. These talks, along with the annual Mutational Scanning Symposium and reading the published literature, have served as the main way by which I find out about new datasets, new methods, and new analysis approaches. Recently, my 5-person lab has started a biweekly “Lunch and Learn” experience, during which we watch one of the VESS presentations, and then discuss how it applies to our work and use it as a jumping off point for more in depth learning about a particular molecular biology, statistics, or computational biology topic. This has been incredibly valuable for my lab, especially for new members, as they are getting to know the field. Thank you to the VESS organizers for making this possible!” Dustin Baldrige - Assistant Professor | Washington University in St. Louis

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The Brotman Baty Institute and the Department of Genome Sciences at the University of Washington, Seattle, USA, provide administrative support on behalf of AVE. The Executive Committee's institutional affiliations are also depicted below.

Along with financial support from the Brotman Baty Institute, [NHGRI](#) has provided initial seed funding for the Alliance through a Center of Excellence in Genome Science grant (NIH NHGRI RM1HGO10461).

WHAT TO LOOK FOR IN 2025

- 8th Annual [Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) in Barcelona May 21-23rd, 2025
- Upgrades and enhancements to our central data repository (MAVEDB)
- Upgrades and enhancements to MaveRegistry
- MAVE Educational Workshops
- Website refresh

OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE AND CONNECT

- [Join the Alliance](#)
- Participate in the monthly Variant Effects Seminar Series ([VESS](#))
- Attend the [Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#)
- Watch educational videos on our [YouTube channel](#) 160 +videos, 900+ subscribers
- Listen to the Variants and Us Podcast [VUSPod](#)
- Check out the [MAVE educational resources](#) on our website
- Register your project or gene of interest on [MaveRegistry](#)

- Deposit your variant effect maps in [MaveDB](#)
- Consider [supporting us!](#)
- Propose a new working or focus group or initiative! (reach out directly to the Director of Program Operations Lara Muffley muffley@uw.edu to discuss)
- Follow and interact
 - [BlueSky](#)
 - [LinkedIn](#)
- [Members](#) of the Alliance can join AVE Slack and post in one of the open channels:
 - ▶ [#educational_resources](#)
 - ▶ [#general](#)
 - ▶ [#introductions](#)
 - ▶ [#job_announcements](#)
 - ▶ [#literature](#)
 - ▶ [#random](#)
 - ▶ [#tips-tricks-troubleshooting](#)
 - ▶ [#variant-effects-seminar-series](#)

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This report was prepared by Lara Muffley.

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The Brotman Baty Institute and the Department of Genome Sciences at the University of Washington, Seattle, USA, provide administrative support on behalf of AVE. For more information about the Alliance please visit <https://www.varianteffect.org/>

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<https://zenodo.org/communities/varianteffect> (10.5281/zenodo.14781483)